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Electronic Voting: A Panacea for Good Governance and Electoral Administration in Nigeria

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Abstract

The complex nature of democracy in African transcends into slow developmental phases we have experienced all through the decades of governance. Transparency cannot be separated from true democracy. Hence, elections and voting are the major determinants of any democratic state. The use of electronic voting (E-Voting) system is pertinent to achieving free and fair election as a pathway to good governance. E-voting will enhance good governance and effective electoral administration that has been deadlock in the past administrative rule. Some African countries have embraced the idea of E-voting in recent time, realizing it will do better than harm. The study will reflect the power of emerging technology (ICT) on electoral administration in Nigeria and also examine the intricacies encountered in the electioneering process through e-voting. Data analyzed in the study will be descriptive, empirical and case studies in highlighting the efficacies of E-voting on governance. However, the paper recommends active use of E-voting system across African society to aid electoral development and good governance. It concludes on proper sensitization of the electoral bodies, the electorates, politicians, governmental bodies in embracing E-voting as a panacea towards effective electoral administration and good governance in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Election, Electronic-Voting (E-voting), Electoral Administration, Governance, Good Governance, Voting.*

Introduction

Governance, election and voting are what informs part of sharpen democracy. What makes a country to achieve these depends largely on how effective structures are put in place. Structures can be determined by welcome innovations, openness, transparency, electoral integrity, Electronic voting has gained a considerable amount of attention in recent years. One feature that has impacted the global economy dramatically would be the growth of information technology.

There are some challenges associated with the traditional electoral system formerly employed by the Electoral Management Bodies (EMB) such as, missing names of some registered voters, intimidation, disfranchisement of voters, multiple and underage voting, snatching or destruction of ballot boxes, miscomputation and falsification of results. These challenges stimulate post-election related violence with the far-reaching consequence of eroding peoples' trust and confidence in the democratic process. With this in view, it is necessary to adopt a better method of the electoral process warranting the need for e-voting.

E-voting for instance has taken place in Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Estonia, France, Germany, India, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Peru, South African, Switzerland, the UK, Venezuela, Pakistan and the Philippines, etc. (News24, 2019). E-voting varies from one country to another and may include voting machines in polling places, centralized tallying of paper ballots and internet voting. Many countries use centralized tallying, some also use electronic voting machines in polling places, while few use internet voting. Several countries have tried electronic approaches and stopped, because of difficulties or concerns about security and reliability. In Africa, countries like Ghana, Namibia, Senegal, Cameroun, Zambia, Kenya, Malawi, Mauritania, Sierra-Leone, Rwanda, had implemented e-voting for one election or the other or as partial adoption of e-voting (Osho, Yisa. and Jebutu, 2022).

Nigeria is adapting to the new technology and using it to their advantage for electoral administration. E-voting has minimized electoral fraud and also reduced unnecessary work load on electioneering in the country since its inception till now. Before now voting had taken a different turn from one INEC Chairman to another

until Prof. Jega introduced partial E-voting into our electoral system through the use of a card reader in 2015. In 2018, Kaduna State became the first state in Nigeria to conduct an election using an electronic voting system. The use of technology since 2011 has initiated a positive trend in improving the quality and integrity of Nigerian elections and the trend should be sustained. In all of these, the surprise is that elections, given their importance to the governance of our societies (Premium Times 2021).

Election administration in Nigeria has taken another shape with emerging technology since 2018 and gradually it is getting better day by day judging from the just concluded Ekiti and Osun state gubernatorial election 2022. The flaws from the use of electronic voting system then and now are more encouraging if going by what we experienced with the new Electoral Act signed by President Muhammadu Buhari cancelling manual accreditation, no use of incident forms, accreditation is electronic and bimodal (facial recognition and fingerprint); and as such, electorates are more tilted towards embracing e-voting for transparency during voting exercise.

Electronic voting requires capital spending every few years to update equipment, as well as annual spending for maintenance, security and supplies. If it works well, its speed can be an advantage where there are many contests on each ballot just as we have in Nigeria. The use of electronic voting will speed up vote counting, cut the cost of paying staff to count votes manually, provide easier access to disabled persons to vote, and funding for elections will decrease. Emerging technology has gained more prominence over the years and its impact in the society cannot be over emphasized. This study will not only project the E-voting as usurper to the liberation of long deceit on our electoral administration but as well create an atmosphere embracing emerging technologies to ease the paper workload, unforeseen disasters, electoral fraud, bureaucratic junks and excellent voting pattern of the westerners.

Statement of Problem & Objectives

The pattern of voting in Nigeria over the years has constantly been changing due to the emerging technology that is fast becoming a reality than we could have thought within a space of decade. Studying the trend and being informed by the practice in the western world on the use of electronic voting for electioneering, all in the bid to achieve free and fair election. Electoral administration in Nigeria has recorded quite a number of flaws in terms of rigging, double voting, vote buying, under-age voting to mention few has betrayed the confidence the masses have on whether our votes count or not. Introduction of E-voting over the traditional method of voting into Nigeria Electoral Act is a welcome idea that is gradually allaying the fears in the heart of the masses showcasing the rightful manner at which election should be conducted. Although e-voting might not totally be the end to electoral fraud and bad governance but will make a giant stride on our democratic system.

The study aims to analyse the impact of electronic voting system across the country for electioneering aiding free and fair election and good governance; while the specifics are to checkmate the intrigues that may come as bane with the use of electronic devices for voting, abuse and impact of effective electoral administration on governance in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

Election

Elections are about choosing, selecting and voting public officials to office to serve the electorate, the people. It is about electing others than you as it is about trust (Mtapuri, O. 2017). Elections form a foundation for a social contract through which the electorate gives the chosen leaders the legitimacy and mandate to govern them (Mapuva, 2013). Election is allowing citizens to articulate their preferences and hold government democracy in which citizens make their choices about the freedom and rights (real and imagined) that they cherish while conferring their citizen power to their representatives who are expected to be accountable to them (Fisher, et al 2013). Election plays

a critical role in democracy, allowing citizens to articulate their preferences and hold the government accountable.

Electronic-Voting (E-Voting)

Electronic voting or e-voting is an electoral process that uses electronic means to enable the casting of ballots, counting of ballots, and transmission of the election results from polling centres to the central office of the electoral management body. It involves the use of electronic voting machines (EVMs) placed in polling stations to ensure a credible non-interference voting system. (Zeenat, 2022). Electronic voting is the use of electronic machines to aid in voting and counting. It works with either computers connected to the Internet or an Electronic Voting Machine (EVM) that records votes by means of a ballot display. The EVM is a computerized box-like machine that comes with an attaching ballot box, where generated ballots drop in that voter use to cast their votes (Premium Times, 2021). E-voting is the use of computer technology that can be used in undertaking such activities as voters' registration exercise, voting and vote counting. Electronic voting (e-voting) is a system that allows voters to send their votes to election officials in a secured and confidential manner over the internet using electronic ballots (Oosteen and Besselar 2019).

Electoral Administration & Electoral Management Bodies (EMB)

Electoral administration is the administrative procedure used for casting ballots and compiling the electoral register (James, 2012). Election administration comprises voter registration, pre-electoral administration, capturing of eligible voters, voting, election observations (civil society), violence, vote counting, post-election recap or election recount and audits. Election administration involves making of rules, application of rules and the implementation of rules according to the dictates of the Electoral Act for electioneering.

Electoral Management Bodies (EMB) are the regulatory bodies that oversee the electioneering process depending on countries that practice democracy. In Nigeria, the body that regulates the conduct of elections is the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC). INEC is a

nonpartisan government agency charged with the conduct and supervision of elections in Nigeria. In the late 1990s, the agency began modernizing its information technology infrastructure by migrating from an outdated legacy voting system heavily dependent on inaccurate paper records and polling cards to the newer Electronic Voting System (EVS). At the heart of EVS is the Electronic Voter Register (EVR), which, by capturing the names of all eligible voters, eliminates duplication and thereby minimizes discrepancies in the electoral process. As such, EVR is viewed as a means of ensuring free and fair elections in Nigeria.

Governance and Good Governance

Governance is "the process of decision-making and the process by which decisions are implemented (or not implemented)" Governance in this context can apply to corporate, international, national, or local governance as well as the interactions between other sectors of society.

Good governance is the process of measuring how public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources, and guarantee the realization of human rights in a manner essentially free of abuse and corruption and with due regard for the rule of law. The concept of "good governance" thus emerges as a model to compare ineffective economies or political bodies with viable economies and political bodies. The concept centers on the responsibility of governments and governing bodies to meet the needs of the masses as opposed to select groups in society.

Voting

Voting is one significant way of expressing one's opinion of choice, and as such, is our civic duty. It is the foremost way to exhibit good citizenship and civil responsibility (Akande, 2019). Voting is a method for a group, such as a meeting or an electorate, in order to make a collective decision or express an opinion usually following discussions, debates or election campaigns (Wiki,2022). In democracy, the election of office holders into office is done through voting. Voting is a right of

all eligible voters in any country. It is seen as the normal or typical form of political activity and it remains the primary means of political participation. The goal of any voting system is to establish the intent of each individual voter and translate those intentions into a final tally or reality. Voting in an election shows your commitment and care about your community, by this, you become engaged with diverse people of the society and the activities of the nation in general.

The Roles of INEC in Ensuring Credible Electoral Exercise in Nigeria

INEC plays a crucial role in implementing of laws that guide electoral processes; voter's registration, creating a balanced playground for all parties, candidates and electorates, overseeing the actual process of conduct of elections, preparing ballot papers and procuring all ballot materials, supervising the balloting process, collating, announcing election results, safe keeping of the ballots, attending to queries and complaints or election related challenges by parties, candidates and promoting transparency at every level of the election (Mapuva, 2010). They also provide election prerequisites as voter information and civic/voter education, spreading awareness on electoral laws, assisting the public to informed choices during the ballot (Mapuva, 2013).

They perform administrative roles by shaping the electoral governmentalities related to the guidelines on (un)acceptable electoral conduct, in other words, establishing the ground rules of the elections and directing the soul and depth of the election in light of the electoral needs of the nation INEC undertakes pre-election tasks which include managing the voter roll and conducting voter education. Some elections require new delimitation of boundaries while identification of polling stations and distribution of electoral resources are other related tasks such that it is not ideal to have a temporary board (Abuya, 2010:125).

INEC introduced the e-voting system to ensure a secured e-collation and results transmission process, a probable option of transferring data would be directly from the EVMs to a main server, and at the same time print hard copies of the results as a back-up. Furthermore, the

deployment and optimal functionality of the BVAS across all the polling units, Registration Area Centres and local government areas of various states involved, is a major statement of how important the role of ICT is especially during the 2023 general elections. For instance, in the Osun state election the Commission successfully circulated its sensitive materials to all the 30 local government areas and 332 Registration Area Centres, with trackers, to ensure that materials are deployed to appropriate locations. Similarly, unlike in previous years, the submission of the details of party agents and list of observers for elections are now done through the online portal. This has further standardized preparations for elections, while evading all forms of backdoor activities and, by extension, ensuring the religious implementation of the activities on the Commission's timeline, going into the election. (Olasupo, 2022).

INEC, being aware of the intricacies involved in election had prepared for upcoming elections of both gubernatorial and presidential by regularly upgrading their electronic devices, updating server, portal, websites for a robust output and accuracy on election results.

Impact of E-Voting System on Governance and Electoral Administration in Nigeria

A cursory look at the introduction of electronic voting into the electoral system in Nigeria is a pathway to good governance in achieving free and fair election to some extent. Most importantly, e-voting reduces human error, increases leisure time, and as more work is done in less time, that results in less paperwork, which gives the INEC the capability to store information, communicate, and transfer data through the internet. Another example would be the invention of the card reader, which has recently become more of an influence in authenticating the voter's card, especially in relation to voting exercise. The Electoral Act 2022 supports technology-driven elections by allowing electronic accreditation, transmission, and collation within statutory law, and this could include AI.

The Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) is the latest technological device introduced into the electoral terrain, which verifies

fingerprints and authenticates facial features to ensure that only those eligible are allowed to vote and prevents voting by proxy. This is steadily making electoral malpractice difficult or impossible, while boosting citizens' confidence in the process. While the BVAS offers a technological leap that improves electoral integrity, the INEC Results Viewing (IREV) Portal and electronic transmission of election results have become a masterstroke that promotes transparency in the results collation process, while preventing malpractice during the physical transmission of results from polling units to collation centres (Olasupo, 2022). This, to a very large extent, enables ordinary citizens to access election results from the comfort of their homes, thereby encouraging accountability in the process.

E-voting is increasingly being seen as the solution to challenges related to vote manipulation and ballot stuffing. Manual vote counting has been minimized by the adoption e-voting method such that Information System and democratic practitioners have been advocating for its adoption, arguing that such a move improves democratic practices (Ahmad, Abdullah and Arshad, 2015). E-voting enhances transparency and accountability by eliminating logistical challenges associated with manual voting (Adetula, 2008). This system, which has been widely used in the developed world, has the advantage of reducing to very minimal levels, challenges relating to accuracy, security and verifiability which are part of the conventional paper-based ballot system (Ahmad, Abdullah and Arshad, 2015).

E-voting enhances electoral efficiency, builds public trust and perception as against traditional voting systems, it reduces human error and large falsification of election results.

Comparison Chart on the Success of E-Voting over Traditional Voting in Nigeria.

Source

ce: Author’s compilation

The chart indicates the asymmetrical decline of the traditional voting system to date and rise in electronic voting in Nigeria. In the early years and introduction of voting exercise in Nigeria, we have experienced traditional voting declining from 4.3% to 1.5% while electronic voting picked up from 1.5% rise to 4.5%. This illustration shows democratic value of electronic voting depends on the technological sophistication of the electoral process and bodies.

Discussions and Findings

Any civilized society is respected by the kind of technologies at its disposal. Emergence of technologies and its introduction into our voting system is a welcome idea which gives democracy an assuring outlook in nature. Electronic voting systems may offer advantages compared to other voting techniques. Hence, can be involved in the setup, distributing, voting, collecting, and counting of ballots, and as such may or may not introduce advantages into any of these steps. Potential disadvantages exist as well including the potential for flaws or weakness in any electronic component. E-voting technology intends to speed the counting of ballots, reduce the cost of paying staff to count votes manually and can provide improved accessibility for disabled

voters. Also in the long term, expenses are expected to decrease, results can be reported and published faster, voters save time, cost by being able to vote independently from their location and this may increase overall voter turnout (Cook, 2016).

Election administration varies from country to country depending on the electoral structures put in place from inception. It is an ongoing activity that reshapes the society and as such speaks loud about the integrity of democracy in that society. In countries like Brazil, electronic voting has been seen as a tool for both reducing electoral fraud and enfranchising individuals with limited literacy by allowing them to vote on a device that is easier to use and can be more graphical in display. Because of cost considerations and concerns about the security and auditability of electronic voting machines, the adoption of this technology in the United States has slowed in more recent years. (Alvarez and Hall 2008a; Saltman 2006). As Norris 2013, 2014, 2015; Norris, Frank, and Martínez I C (2014) has argued, election administration is a difficult task and is challenged not only when overt acts of election fraud occur vote buying, intimidation, and ballot-box stuffing but also when election malpractice occurs. Such malpractice might include errors in voter registries, failures to follow appropriate standard operating procedures, or problems with counting ballots.

The first ever electronic voting exercise happened in Kaduna State in 2015, in Dr. (Mrs.) Saratu Binta Dikko-Audu, Chairman of the Kaduna State Independent Electoral Commission (KAD-SIECOM) in her words, “This [technology] is wonderful because there is really no chance of manipulating the results as the machine captures what has been input and prints it out at the end of the election and once it’s printed out; data cannot be changed from any end.” By itself, the EVM has a failsafe mechanism. If a wrong password is entered three times, it powers off in 15 seconds until restarted again. All these security measures in place give the impression that nothing can ever go wrong (Techpoint.africa, 2018).

Bane in the use of Electronic Voting System

However, e-voting may pose some challenges from cybersecurity risk, digital inequality and accessibility and the huge cost of advanced technology or equipment. There are more concerns on the Electoral Management Bodies (INEC) site being hacked, low internet penetration by service providers, ignorance by the electorates and intolerance by the electoral officers. Electronic voting requires capital spending every few years to update equipment, as well as annual spending for maintenance, security and supplies. Some countries have tried electronic approaches and stopped, because of difficulties or concerns about security and reliability. Estonia in 2005 suffered a cyber-attack and in the 2007 election did not pull back and still made use of electronic voting.

The Future of E-Voting on Electoral Administration in Nigeria

While electronic voting systems can improve accessibility for persons with disabilities, diaspora voters and literate citizens. It holds great potential to strengthen democratic processes, the long-standing electoral weaknesses, voter impersonation, multiple registrations, manual errors, movement of sensitive materials and reducing manipulation windows.

Source: Author’s compilation

This graph is an illustration of how the e-voting system has gained more recognition and acceptability in Nigeria judging from the outcome of electioneering processes so far. In 2015, partial e-voting was introduced through the use of card reader (25%); In 2018, e-voting was first used for electioneering in Kaduna state (35%); In 2019, it was widely used for general election (55%); In 2022 it was used in Ekiti and Osun state for gubernatorial election (65%); then in 2023 general election (70%) which was a success and there is no doubt that it will not be used for coming elections in Nigeria based on its reliability/acceptability.

The Chairman of the CDD Election Analysis Centre, Prof. Adele Jinadu, stated this while presenting the report on the Osun governorship election in Abuja. According to him, the organization deployed 300 trained and accredited observers, adding that data indicated that in at least 92 per cent of polling units observed, critical election materials like ballot papers, BVAS devices, results' sheets, ballot boxes and the voter register were available for the conduct of the election, a marked improvement over the 83 per cent recorded in Ekiti. He said, "(The) CDD-EAC notes that the Independent National Electoral Commission took some steps to address some of the gaps identified in the Ekiti State governorship election last month. "The mock accreditation exercise carried out by INEC to ensure the readiness of the 5,306 BVAS machines appears to have worked, with the CDD-EAC officials noting that there was a BVAS machine and compliance at various polling units (Olokor, 2022).

In addition, there has been a lot of improvement from INEC through the use of e-voting for electioneering. Efforts were made in different capacities during the concluded general election and after by laying groundwork for a fully modernized, tech enabling system.

Conclusion and Recommendations

ICT is the new generation and as such, the world will keep up with this new innovation. Governance without technology will not thrive, thus, it is important to fully focus on the deployment of innovative technologies in our electoral process. Our ability to develop innovative applications

to solve many other problems can be extended to improve our electoral system through the power of digital technologies. Poor electoral administration can lead to consequences, i.e., breach of trust and undermining our democracy, if care is not taken it could lead to protest and aggravate economic disorderliness. In that regard, e-voting will promote electoral transparency, integrity and build public trust.

In the desire for good governance and effective electoral administration, INEC officials, ad-hoc staff should undergo training in handling electronic devices for the electioneering process and electorates should be sensitized more on the many benefits of e-voting. INEC should intensify more efforts on the search for relevant technologies that will enhance voting patterns and habits in coming elections. Against the background of cyber-safety, past attacks on INEC websites and portals, INEC should consider implementing strong security protocols, advanced data encryption and security data tunnels for secured data transmission towards the development of election administration in Nigeria in the nearest future. The Government should not relent in providing maximum support in the areas of adequate security, strong financial base capacity to purchase necessary equipment for electioneering.

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